

INNOVATIVE FIN-TECHNOLOGIES IN BANKS

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Abstract. Nowadays, the emergence of innovative services in banks, as well as their convenience, offer customers a lot of comfort. This article will talk about fin - technology, in which it will mainly talk about digital technologies and their impact on customers. It is also briefly cited about the innovative services, facilities and benefits they provide.

Keywords: fintech, online and mobile banking, ATMs, biometric authentication, Open Banking and APIs, Low code/ no code.

Introduction.

Importance of the topic. In the conditions of the digital economy, changes in consumer demands, cost reduction and high pressure to increase efficiency are driving commercial banks to modern digital technologies. Also, the increase in demand for online services in banks, in turn, created an incentive for Fintech companies to become participants.

Fintech means financial innovations based on the use of digital technologies and big data. At the same time, the use of digital technologies helps to increase financial efficiency and improve services. Also, the increasingly widespread use of Fintech technology provides an opportunity to automate banking operations, and customers can make payments using mobile phones and tablets (mobile banking). Therefore, bank employees should play a more advisory role than directly implementing operations.

Fintech is made up of two words: fin and tech. Fin is financial and tech is for technology. When financial products are serviced using digital technologies, it is called Fintech. This is the simplest meaning of Fintech. Usually, this is SaaS (software as a service). SaaS refers to where software is provided to users as a service. SaaS is prevalent in most of the FinTech industry. For example, when you do an online translation using a digital platform, it is considered in Fintech. FinTech companies are the ones who have developed the whole mechanism for this.

The evolving fintech technology service in the banking sector is having a significant impact on loans such as personal loans, small business loans and mortgages. The concept of traditional banking is being radically changed through digitization and technological innovation. Currently, the bank's mobile application provides fast customer service and replaces the role of the bank's traditional sales manager.

Research methods.

The banking system has evolved significantly over the years with the integration of various technologies to improve efficiency, security and customer experience. In particular, some of the main technologies used in today's modern banking system are:

Online and mobile banking: are digital services provided by financial institutions that allow customers to manage their accounts, make transactions and access various banking services through the Internet or mobile applications. These technologies have revolutionized the way people interact with their money, providing convenience, accessibility and real-time control over their money. Online and Mobile Banking Overview:

Online banking:

1. Account Login: Customers can login to the bank's website using a secure username and password. Once logged in, they can view their account balances, transaction history, and other account information.

2. Transaction Management: Online banking allows customers to perform a wide range of operations such as transferring funds between accounts, paying bills, setting up recurring payments, and ordering checks.

3. Accounts: Users can access and download electronic account statements, which can be useful for tracking expenses and financial planning.

4. Mobile Check Deposit: Some online banking platforms allow customers to deposit checks by taking an image of the check using their mobile phone. This eliminates the need to visit a physical bank branch.

5. Communication: Customers can send secure messages to their bank's customer service representatives for inquiries or assistance.

6. Security: Banks employ various security measures such as encryption, multi-factor authentication, and account activity alerts to protect confidential customer information.

ATMs (automated teller machines): are self-service electronic devices that allow customers to perform various banking transactions without directly interacting with bank employees. ATMs have become a ubiquitous part of the modern banking landscape, providing the convenience and accessibility of banking services 24/7.

Functions of ATMs:

1. Cash withdrawal: One of the main functions of an ATM is to give cash to account holders. Customers can use their debit or ATM cards to withdraw cash from their checking or savings account.

2. Deposits: Many ATMs allow customers to deposit cash or checks directly into their accounts. Some advanced ATMs can accept multiple checks at once, accurately count cash, and provide instant receipts.

3. Balance Inquiry: Users can check their account balance to monitor their financial status.

4. Fund Transfers: ATMs can facilitate money transfers between linked accounts in the same bank.

5. Bill Pay: Some ATMs offer bill pay, which allows customers to pay utility bills, credit card payments, or other expenses directly at the machine. offers opportunities.

6. Mini Statements: Customers can request a mini statement of their recent account transactions.

7. Change PIN: Users can change their ATM or debit card PIN for security purposes.

8. Mobile top-up: ATMs in some areas allow customers to top up their prepaid mobile phone accounts.

9. Donate: Some ATMs offer the option of donating to charities.

Biometric authentication: A technology that uses a person's unique physical or behavioral characteristics to verify their identity. It offers a more secure and convenient way to authenticate users than traditional methods like passwords or PINs. Biometric authentication is increasingly being integrated into various industries, including banking. Here's an overview of biometric authentication and its role in banking:

Biometric authentication types:

1. Fingerprint Identification: This is one of the most common forms of biometric authentication. Users place their finger on the sensor and the system matches the fingerprint pattern stored in its database.

2. Facial recognition: This technology captures and analyzes facial features to confirm identity. It is often used in mobile devices and other applications.

3. Recognizing the iris: The complex patterns in the colored part of the eye (iris) are unique to each individual. Iris recognition involves capturing and comparing these patterns for authentication.

4. Voice recognition: Voice tracks are created by analyzing the unique characteristics of the human voice, such as pitch, pitch, and cadence.

5. Behavioral biometrics: This involves analyzing how a person interacts with a device, such as typing speed, mouse movements, and touch screen gestures.

It is important to note that while biometric authentication offers many advantages, there are also privacy, security and biometric data storage issues. Banks must implement robust security measures to protect biometric data from unauthorized access or tampering. In addition, individuals should be aware of how their biometric information is used and stored by financial institutions.

Results and their discussion. Open Banking and APIs: Open banking refers to the practice of sharing financial information and services through standardized APIs. This allows customers to allow third-party providers, such as fintech companies, to access financial data held by banks. The goal of Open Banking is to create an interconnected and competitive financial ecosystem that gives consumers more control over their financial information and access to a wider range of innovative products and services.

Key aspects of open banking: data sharing, customer satisfaction, innovation, competition, APIs.

API (Software Programming Interfaces): APIs are sets of rules and protocols that allow different software applications to communicate and interact with each other. In the context of open banking, APIs provide tools for authorized third-party providers to securely access banking data and services.

Open Banking API Use Cases: Account Information Services (AIS), Payment Initiation Services (PIS), Fund Transfers, Personal Financial Management (PFM), Lending and Credit Scoring.

Open banking and APIs have the potential to transform the financial landscape by driving collaboration, innovation and customer-centric solutions.

However, they raise important considerations related to data privacy, security and regulatory compliance that must be carefully managed to protect customer data and ensure confidence in the financial ecosystem.

In the graph above, we can see the number of users of open banking around the world, divided by region over the past 5 years. For all given years, the largest number of users are located in the European region, which reached 12 million by 2020, growing rapidly in the following years and is expected to exceed 64 million in 2024.

In addition, we can see that the other 4 given regions are also growing rapidly, but Latin America has shown the lowest performance in these years: despite having almost 1 million users in 2020, 4 As a result of annual growth, this figure is expected to reach approximately 6 million by 2024.

Figure 1. The number of open banking service users worldwide (in millions).

Low code/ no code : development platforms offer a way to create applications with minimal manual coding, which makes developing software solutions easier and faster. In the banking system, these platforms can be used to solve various problems, simplify processes and improve customer experience. Here are some ways to use low code/no code in banking:

1. Digital banking applications;
2. Launch the client;
3. Loan application and approval;
4. Chatbots and customer support;
5. Risk management and compliance;
6. Data analysis and reporting;
7. Customer relationship management (CRM);
8. Process automation;
9. Payment and transaction solutions;
10. Innovation and prototyping.

Benefits of low code/no code in banking: speed and agility, cost efficiency, business-IT collaboration, innovation, customization, user experience, scalability.

While low code/no code platforms offer significant advantages, they may not be suitable for all banking use cases, especially those that require highly complex integrations or specialized functionality. It is important for banks to carefully assess the strengths and limitations of these platforms and choose the right approach based on their specific needs and goals.

Summary

In conclusion, it can be said that Fintech technology is not only developing this industry with its conveniences in banking, but also creating several conveniences in customer service. Also, in order to ensure the transparency of banking operations in foreign banks, this technology has shown its effect, and the introduction of this technology in our country also makes us happy. The most used services in the activity of banks is lending. Digitization of this sector is currently

underway to create a very convenient sector for banks and create convenient opportunities for customers.

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